

ECO-EFFICIENTLY CURED AND HALOGEN-FREE FLAME RETARDANT COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this contribution, we show that it is possible to obtain halogen-free flame retardant (FR) fibre reinforced composites by using UV-curable difunctional acrylated phosphorus containing oligomers. UD glass fabrics were selected as fibre reinforcement and these fabrics were impregnated by padding with a polymer resin formulation containing different concentrations of the FR oligomer. The final composite structures were obtained by stacking five impregnated layers on top of each other, followed by UV curing of the complete stack. The influence of the FR oligomer concentration on the flame retardant properties as well as on the flexural properties of the composites are presented and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced polymer composites play already an important role in our daily lives. These materials are lightweight and have high strengths especially in the direction of the fibre. They are used in buildings, automotive, aerospace, sport articles and consumer goods.

The fibres are usually glass, carbon or aramid although other fibres such as basalt, polypropylene (PP), flax and hemp are more and more utilized. The matrix can be a thermosetting plastic (e.g. epoxy, vinylester, polyester) or thermoplastic (e.g. PP). [1-3]

The curing step of the thermosetting matrix is often one of the most time consuming steps in composite manufacturing. This means long processing times and slow production rates. Also a lot of energy is needed during the curing steps. These two factors lead to high production costs and composite manufacturers are looking for alternative methods to speed up the process. [4]

Another possibility to crosslink or cure resins is using radiation energy instead of thermal convection. UV curing is one of the most well known methods and is already frequently utilized in the wood and graphical sector. UV curing is a very fast process and will therefore significantly reduce the production time. Secondly, UV curable formulations are either solvent free (100% systems) or water based, resulting in a very low VOC emission. UV curing systems also require less energy and space compared to large and high energy consuming thermal ovens. This makes UV curing a sustainable and eco-friendly curing technology. [5, 6]

UV curable matrix formulations require special chemistries such as UV curable resins (mostly acrylate type of binders), viscosity modifiers (thickening agents for water based systems, viscosity reducers, i.e. monomers, for 100% systems) and photoinitiators. The resins can be epoxy or polyester based making them interesting composite matrix material.

However, a disadvantage of UV curing is the limited penetration depth of UV light. Material that is not exposed to UV light will not cure. This also means that UV curing is mainly used for repairing purposes in the composite industry or for filament winding processes. [7, 8]

Fortunately, there are possibilities to increase the curing depth, namely 1) selecting UV transparent fibres, 2) using through-cure photoinitiators and 3) using UVA radiation. Specifically UVA-LED lamps are very interesting. Unlike conventional UV curing, UVA-LED systems only emit narrowband UVA light meaning that no toxic ozone is formed and no thermal stress from IR radiation occurs. [9] The combination of these 3 factors opens opportunities to cure relatively thick composite panels by UV radiation.

For many applications, fibre reinforced polymer composites have to be flame retardant. However, most polymer matrix materials burn quite easily. This can be solved by adding flame retardants, which are often halogenated, into the matrix formulation or by using intrinsically flame retardant resins, e.g. phenolic or furan resins which are cured thermally. [10, 11]

In this paper we show another possibility to obtain halogen-free flame retardant polyester/glass composites by adding a difunctional acrylated phosphorus containing oligomer in the 100% UV curable matrix formulation. This approach combines the speed of UV curing with good FR properties of the resulting composite material. The phosphorus is covalently bonded to the polymer which makes leaching out impossible. Furthermore the FR resin crosslinks with the other UV curable components resulting in a uniform distribution in the matrix.

UD glass fabrics were selected as fibre reinforcement as they have good mechanical properties and are also UVA transparent which is required for through-curing with UV-light. Firstly, prepregs were prepared by means of a padding process and full curing was achieved by using UV-LED light. Secondly, the influence of the FR resin concentration on the flexural and FR properties was investigated

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

Glass UD fabrics were bought from MC Technics. The chemicals were supplied by BASF and Allnex.

2.2 Synthesis

Four 100% UV systems were prepared by mixing a polyester acrylate (PES acrylate), a monomer thinner, FR resin and photoinitiator at room temperature. The composition of the matrix of the four samples is shown in table 1.

Sample	PES acrylate (%)	Monomer (%)	FR resin (%)	Photoinitiator (%)
1	9	27	60	4
2	24	27	45	4
3	39	27	30	4
4	69	27	0	4

Table 1: matrix composition.

The glass UD fabrics were impregnated with the formulations by padding. The final composite structures were obtained by stacking five impregnated layers on top of each other (hand lay-up), followed by UV-LED curing of the complete stack. The power of the lamp was 12 W/cm², the output wavelength was 395 nm and the samples were passed 5 times at a speed of 6.67 m/min under the lamp.

2.3 Characterization

To determine the flexural modulus and strength of the UV-cured composites, a three point bending test (ISO 14125) was performed on the 4 samples.

The burning behaviour of the four composite samples was tested via method FAR 25.853. This method involves the ignition of the edge of the samples during 60 s by a flame from a Bunsen. The flame duration after removing the Bunsen, the flame progress and the presence of melted droplets are monitored. To pass this test the flame duration must be lower or equal then 15 s and the flame progress should be lower or equal than 155 mm. Furthermore, no molten polymer droplets are allowed.

Besides the burning behaviour also the optical smoke density (Airbus Industries Test Method (AITM) 2.0007:1993) and smoke toxicity (AITM 3.0005:1993) were determined. For the smoke density test, a sample is ignited and the smoke density after 4 minutes (DS_{max} 0-4) is measured. The average (D_m) value of three tests should be lower than 150. For the smoke toxicity, the concentration of six toxic gases, i.e. HCN, CO, NO_x , SO_2 , HF and HCl, is determined and should be respectively lower than 150, 1000, 100, 100, 100 and 15 ppm.

3 RESULTS

After curing the samples, which have thicknesses around 2.5 mm, are dry and stiff which shows that UV-LED radiation is an interesting technique for composite curing. Furthermore padding (Foulard) is a feasible method for preparing impregnated fabrics (i.e. prepregs). This also opens opportunities for the textile coating and finishing industry as this industry is used to work with roll-to-roll padding processes.

The flexural modulus and strength of the four composite samples were determined and are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: flexural modulus and stiffness of UV cured polyester acrylate composites containing 60, 45, 30 and 0% FR resin obtained by the 3-point bending test.

The flexural modulus of the samples with 0, 30 and 60% FR resin is around 9 GPa while the sample containing 45% FR resin in the matrix has a modulus of 7 GPa. However, the error bars are overlapping meaning that the FR resin has no significant influence on the flexural modulus.

The flexural strength of the composite samples is between 120 and 140 MPa. Similar as for the modulus, the addition of FR resin has no significant impact on the flexural strength indicating that this is a good alternative to make UV cured polyester/glass composites flame retardant without the need of adding extra FR additives which can leach out of the composite.

Figure 2: UV-LED cured composites after burning containing from left to right 0%, 30%, 45% and 60% FR UV curable resin.

The results of the flame tests of the 4 samples are presented in figure 2 and table 2. The picture of the burnt samples in figure 2 clearly shows that the addition of more FR resin leads to less flame propagation. Table 2 gives some more detailed information. The sample with 60% FR resin extinguish almost immediately after flame removal, showing a very good FR property. Decreasing the amount of FR resin leads to longer flame duration times and when no FR additive is added also no FR behaviour is observed. As the matrix is thermoset, no droplets are formed during burning for all the samples. The samples with 60% and 45% FR resin have flame duration times below the threshold value of 15 s, but only the sample with 60% FR resin has a burnt length lower than 15 cm. This means that only this sample passes the test.

FR content (%)	flame ignition time (s)	flame duration (s)	flame progress (cm)	droplets
60	60	1	14.5	no
45	60	8	17	no
30	60	48	21.5	no
0	60	240*	29*	no

* reached the top of the sample; no self-extinguishment

Table 2: results from the FAR 25.853 test.

The smoke density and toxicity tests were only performed on the sample with 60% FR resin as it is the only sample that passed the FAR 25.853 flame test. The selected smoke density test is a quite severe test as it is used for aerospace materials.

Time (min)	1	1.5	2	3	4	5	6	DSmax 0-4 min
Test 1	11	100	226	320	366	374	366	366
Test 2	55	176	236	302	345	343	333	345
Test 3	6	54	195	336	381	376	361	381

Average D_m : 364

Standard deviation: 18

Table 3: optical smoke density results for the UV-LED composite containing 60% FR resin.

The results of 3 measurements are given in table 3. The average value (D_m) is higher than the limit value, meaning that too much smoke is generated during burning and the material has not passed the test.

On the other hand, the smoke toxicity results shown in table 4 reveal that the concentration of toxic gases is below the exposure limits for all the determined gases. When the measured value is far below the minimum threshold value it is not required to perform extra tests. Therefore only for the CO determination two extra tests were performed as the measured value was higher than 50% of the maximal allowed value.

However, the value is still below the exposure limit of 100 ppm. This means that although these materials cannot be used for airplane interior applications due to the high smoke density, they can be used for other applications where good FR properties are required and smoke density is less critical.

Gas	HCN (ppm)	CO (ppm)	NO _x (ppm)	SO ₂ (ppm)	HF (ppm)	HCl (ppm)
Test 1	0	750	1	10	0	0
Test 2	-	600	-	-	-	-
Test 3	-	750	-	-	-	-
Average	0	700	1	10	0	0
Limit	150	1000	100	100	100	150

Table 4: determination of toxic gas substances present in smoke coming from the UV-cured composite containing 60% FR resin.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this report, it is shown that UV-LED curing is a fast and eco-efficient technique for curing glass fibre reinforced polymer composites and padding is an easy process for impregnating the fibre reinforcement in a continuous way.

Furthermore, excellent flame retardant properties can be obtained by incorporating 60% of a halogen-free UV curable FR resin in the composite matrix without reducing the flexural strength and modulus of the composite material.

When exposed to flames there is large formation of smoke, but this smoke contains only a little amount of toxic gases and the values are far below the limit values defined for interior airplane materials.

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